

Supplementary Material - 2

Article: Accuracy of remote diagnosis of oral mucositis in children and adolescents with cancer using a mobile application: a pilot study

- True Positive (OM - Left buccal mucosa region).

- True Positive (SOM - Lip region).

- False positive (OM - Lip region).

- False positive (OM - Right lateral region of the tongue).

- There were no records of false negatives.